
Awareness of B.Ed. Students of Jamia Millia Islamia about Madarsa Education: A Descriptive Study

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to explore the awareness of B.Ed. First Year Students of Jamia Millia Islamia about Madaras Education. Further, this study seeks to shed light on the ways in which a supportive and inclusive school environment can be provided to the prospective teacher, which can positively impact students' personality. A self-developed questionnaire was used to collect data from the B.Ed. first year students. The result shows that the B.Ed. students of Jamia Millia Islamia have high awareness level about the basic concept of Madrasa and have moderate level of awareness regarding Madrasa education. This may be due to the fact that mostly students were from Muslim community, and most of them were studied in Maktab (primary). Contrary to this, those students who were from CBSE and other Boards have a very less awareness about madrasa education. It was also reported by respondents that the role of Madrasa education is a key contributor for the holistic development of a child personality.

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INTRODUCTION

The term *madrasa* (also spelled *madrrasah*) is an Arabic term that means "school" or "place of learning." In Islamic contexts, it typically refers to an educational institution where students study various subjects, including Quran, Islamic theology, jurisprudence and law (Sharia), and Arabic language, among other subjects such as science, mathematics, and literature. Any educational establishment, from preschool to high school, is referred to as a *madrasa* in contemporary Arabic.

In the words of Peter and Pandey (2006), *madrasas* differ from nation to nation or even from city to city. They may be day or residential schools, general educational institutions, or exclusively religious schools connected to mosques. *Madrasa* has historically been and still is a center of learning for Muslims (Ellis, 2007).

Madrasa education in India holds significance as it plays a crucial role in imparting Islamic teachings, fostering cultural and societal understanding, and preserving linguistic traditions. It contributes to the value and moral education of all communities, promoting a holistic approach to learning that goes beyond academics (Khan, 2022). Additionally, *madrasas* can serve as centers for community development and social cohesion. In addition, it offers free boarding and accommodation, and free education to the all students (Soni, 2010).

Madrasa education in a society can have a profound impact by preserving cultural, societal and religious heritage, fostering a strong sense of brotherhood, harmony and peace in the personality of every individual, and providing a foundation for moral and ethical values and contributing to social welfare through charitable activities (Khan, 2010).

Madrasa education plays a crucial role in the holistic development of a child by providing a comprehensive foundation that includes religious, moral, cultural and scientific knowledge. It instills values, ethics, and a strong sense of nature and personality of a child, contributing to the child's spiritual and emotional well-being. Additionally, *madrasas* often emphasize discipline, community engagement, and linguistic skills, fostering a well-rounded education that goes beyond traditional academics. This holistic approach aims to shape individuals who are not only academically proficient but also ethically grounded and culturally aware (Azmi, 2023).

However, the impact can vary, and there is ongoing debate about modernizing and integrating *madrasa* education to address contemporary challenges. Because in some regions, the term has been misunderstood or used to refer only to institutions teaching religious ideology, but many *madrasas* also offer a broad curriculum that includes mathematics, social science, science, and literature. As we know that the person who reviews the history of *madrasa* education finds a lot of contribution of *madrasas*.

The cradle of new technologies and new civilizations during the Middle Ages was the madrasa. It is indisputable that madrasas have played a significant role in the political and educational rebirth of our nation. It served as the launchpad for the fight for liberation. It was the home of Intellectuals, poets, authors, and revolutionaries. Each system of education has a unique past. The past serves as a kind of reflection for it. But unfortunately, now numerous gaps exist between the madrasa education in those days and contemporary madrasa education (Talha,2015).

Jamia Millia Islamia is a centrally Muslim minority institute may possess a good understanding of Islamic principles, madrasa curriculum, and languages, which can enhance their ability to educate them who are coming from madrasa along with other Integrating elements of madrasa education into teacher training programs can promote cultural a diverse perspective in educational institutions.

This research delves into the understanding, perceptions, and awareness of B.Ed. students of Jamia Millia Islamia towards the madrasa education in the broader educational landscape. By examining the awareness levels, the study aims to shed light on how these prospective educators perceive the contributions of madrasa education to the holistic development of individuals and communities. Through a detailed exploration, the research seeks to provide valuable insights into the integration of diverse educational perspectives in teacher training programs. Finding of this research can be used to develop evidence-based policies, teaching methods, and interventions that enhance the overall development of a child personality who are from madrasa along with all students.

2. METHODS AND MATERIALS

Survey method is adopted by the researcher for this study. The approach used in this research is a quantitative approach through descriptive analysis.

2.1. PARTICIPANTS: First year students of B.Ed. and B.Ed. special Education of Jamia Millia Islamia were selected by using Purposive sampling. There was a total of 40 participants comprising from B.Ed. and from B.Ed. Special.

2.2. TOOLS: In order to collect the data researcher developed an unstructured questionnaire. The questionnaire contains 26 items. The questionnaire was validated by 3experts in the field.

2.3. DATA COLLECTION: In inform consent was obtained from all the participants before responding on questionnaire. After that data was collected by administering the questionnaire. 30 minutes were given to the participants for responding on the questionnaire.

2.4. ANALYSIS: Obtained data were tabulated and entered into M. S. Excell sheet. Then descriptive statistical analysis was used to analyze the data.

3. RESULTS

Table 1: Responses of B.Ed. students of Jamia Millia Islamia(N=40) about Madrasa

NO	STATEMENT	NO OF RESPONSES	
		Yes	No
1	Were you aware of the term "Madrasa Education" before taking this survey?	Yes	No
		39	1
2	Do you believe that Madrasa education provides valuable skills for students?	33	7
3	Have you visited any Islamic Madrasa?	31	9
4	Studying in Madrasa is a challenging task in 21 st century in India.	27	13
5	Do you think Madrasa Education adequately prepares students for modern worlds?	24	16
6	Madrasa Education will improve my personality.	32	8
7	Madrasa provides an appropriate environment for scientific and modern education.	29	11
8	Madrasa Education is being provided to give Quran, Hadith, and Fiqh to their students.	40	0
9	Are you aware that candidate has Fazilat Degree from any recognized madrasa is eligible to apply for Pre-Tib (BUMS).	22	18
10	The degrees of Molvi, Alim, and Fazil are considered equivalent in the general education.	23	17

Table 1 shows that 97 % (39) B.Ed. first year students were aware of the term of “Madrasa Education” before taking this survey while 3 % B.Ed. students were not aware. They told they have studied about madrasa education and have listened very much about madrasa in the society (family, friends, imam of masjid), television and also, they have visited madrasa.

A total of 84 % B.Ed 1st year students of Jamia Millia Islamia believe that that Madrasa education provides valuable skills for students, while 16 % don't believe on the statement. Further, B.Ed. 1st year students around 77 % visited Islamic Madrasa, while 23 % did not visit. The data reveals that 67 % respondents are agreed that Studying in Madrasa is a challenging task in 21st century in India while 33 % did not accept it. Sixty percent B.Ed.1st year students think Madrasa Education adequately prepares students for modern worlds and 40% think Madrasa Education does not adequately prepare students for modern worlds. When the participants were asked whether madrasa education will improve your personality or not. Then 80 % B.Ed. students of Jamia Millia Islamia agree that Madrasa Education will improve my personality. 20 % don't agree for it. Majority of the B.Ed. students of Jamia Millia Islamia agree that Madrasa provides an appropriate environment for scientific and modern education while 28 % students are not agreed that Madrasa provides an appropriate environment for scientific and modern education. A total sample of B.Ed. students of Jamia Millia Islamia is aware that Madrasa Education is being provided to give Quran, Hadith, and Fiqh to their students. There was no one who is not aware of it. This data shows that 55 % respondents are aware that candidate has Fazilat Degree from any recognized madrasa is eligible to apply for Pre-Tib (BUMS), while 45 % were unaware of it. Mostly students don't know the differences among Molvi, alim and fazil. Therefore 67 % students said yes while Molvi, Alim, and Fazil are not considered equivalent in the general education because the degree of molvi is considered to be equivalent to high school (class 10th), Alim (class 12th) and Fazeelat (class 12th and graduation) while 33 % respondents were aware.

Table 2: Responses of B.Ed. students of Jamia Millia Islamia(N=40) about Madrasa

NO	STATEMENT	NO OF RESPONSES	
		Right	Wrong
1	The word 'Hafiz' is used for....	37	3
2	Alimiyat degree is considered to be equivalent to....	28	12
3	Maktab is considered to be equivalent to....	25	15
4	According to Sachar Committee Report, how many percent of Muslim population are in Madrasa Education?	10	30
5	SPQEM stands for....	33	7
6	How many types of madrasas are in India?	23	17
7	Mostly Religious Madrasas are funded by....	37	3

8	Aided madrasa means...	23	17
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Majority of the students (92 %) of the B.Ed. of Jamia Millia Islamia are aware of the word ‘Hafiz’ while 8 % were not aware of the word ‘Hafiz’. Further, 70 % students were aware that Alimiyat degree is considered to be equivalent to Inter College (12th) therefore gave correct answer while 30 % were unaware because they have chosen wrong option and 62 % respondents of B.Ed. were aware that Maktab is considered to be equivalent to Primary School (5th) while 38 % were unaware because they have chosen wrong option. The data shows that majority of the students is unaware. Only 25 % students are aware that 2.5 % of Muslim population are in Madrasa Education. Mostly respondents around 82% are aware that SPQEM stands for “Scheme for Providing Quality Education in Madrasa” while 18 % were unaware of it. The result shows that 57 % respondents are aware that how many types of madrasas are in India while 43 % are unaware. Majority of the B.Ed. 1st year students of Jamia Millia Islamia are aware that mostly religious madrasas are funded by Islamic charities while 8 % are unaware of it. And also 57 % respondents are aware of the meaning of aided madrasa while 43 % are unaware.

Table 3: Responses of B.Ed. students of Jamia Millia Islamia(N=40) about Madrasa

NO	STATEMENT	RESPONSES
1	Madrasa is for:	
A	Islamic theology	1
B	Islamic Education	17
C	Modern and Islamic education	22
D	Maktab	0

2	What is your perception of the quality of education provided in Madrasas?	
A	Excellent	11
B	Good	13
C	Average	14
D	Poor	2
3	In your opinion, how can awareness of Madrasa	

	education be improved through?	
A	Increased media coverage	1
B	Educational programs	17
C	Community outreach	12
D	Government initiatives	10
4	What is the primary focus of Madrasa education?	
A	Religious and Islamic education	14
B	General education	0
C	Both	26
D	Only Arabic	0
5	What sources have contributed to your understanding of madrasa education? You may choose more than one option.	
A	School curriculum	10 (ce)
B	Media (TV, News, etc.)	6 (bcde)
C	Society (Family, Friends, etc.)	19 (c)
D	Internet	5 (ace)
E	Religious institutions	
6	Article 30 of the Indian constitution gives right...	
A	To conserve their language, culture, and script	12
B	To stablish institutions for their choice	19
C	Right to education	3
D	Equality and Equity	6
7	Is there any government rules and regulations for establishing Madrasa?	
A	Yes	23
B	No	5

C	Not sure	12
8	In your opinion, Madrasa plays a vital role in Muslim society.	
A	Yes	35
B	No	2
C	Not sure	3

1. When they were asked what type of education is being provided by madrasa. 55 % students supported c option (modern and Islamic education), 43 % b option (Islamic education) and 2 % 'a' option (Islamic theology) and nobody supported d (maktab). So, majority is aware of the concept of madrasa.
2. This shows that quality of education provided in Madrasas are good and also, they are aware of quality of education provided in madrasa. Because 27 % students are agreed that quality of education provided in Madrasas are excellent, 33% good, 35 % average and 5 % poor.
3. The fig. shows that 43 % students are agreed that awareness of Madrasa education can be improved through educational program, 30 % through Community outreach, 25 % through Government initiatives and 2% increased media coverage.
4. The awareness of respondents regarding the primary of madrasa education are very less. Only 35 % students are aware that What is the primary focus of Madrasa education while 65 % were unaware.
5. This fig. shows mostly students are aware through society. 25 % students are aware through society and religious institutes, 15 % through media, society, internet, and religious institutions, 47 % society, 13% school curriculum, society and religious institutions. This figure shows majority of the students are aware through society.
6. Around 47 % students are aware of Article 30 of the Indian constitution. (right to establish and administer educational institution for their choice) while 30 %, 15 % and 8% (total 53%) are unaware of Article 30 of the Indian constitution.
7. Fifty seven percent respondents are aware while 13 % are not aware and 30 % are not sure. So total 43 % students are not aware of government rules and regulations for establishing Madrasa.
8. Mostly respondents (87%) of B.Ed. of Jamia Millia Islamia are agreed that, madrasa plays a vital role in Muslim society. 5 % are not agreed and 8 % are not sure.

4. DISCUSSION

The findings of the study highlight several important issues regarding the level of awareness of the B.Ed. students of Jamia Millia Islamia about the madrasa education. Around 84 % B.Ed. students of Jamia Millia Islamia believe that that Madrasa education provides valuable skills for students and also mostly madrasas provide religious and cultural education, not valuable skills for this world. Mostly respondents are agreed that studying in Madrasa is a challenging task in 21st century in India. Because mostly students who come from madrasa face many problems and difficulties in modern education.

Around 60 % B.Ed. students think that Madrasa Education adequately prepares students for modern worlds while 40% B.Ed. students don't agree. They say madrasa don't provide modern education but they provide Islamic education. They provide a little a bit modern education like English language, computer, basic math, and basic science that are not sufficient for modern education system. Only 40% respondents are aware that Madrasa education does not adequately prepare students for modern worlds. Majority (80%) of B.Ed. students believe that madrasa education will improve my personality if they get madrasa education. Majority (72%) of the B.Ed. students of Jamia Millia Islamia agree that Madrasa provides an appropriate environment for scientific and modern education. It shows that majority of the students is unaware of the madrasa education.

Only 25 % respondents are aware that 2.5 % of Muslim population are in Madrasa Education, as per Sachar Committee Report. The data revealed that fifty five percent of the respondents are aware about the degree of madrasa that are considered to be equivalent to modern education. And 57 % of B.Ed. students of Jamia Millia Islamia are aware that how many types of madrasas are in India while 43 % are unaware.

Some (27 %) of the students are agreed that quality of education provided in Madrasas are excellent, 33% good, 35 % average and a few students (5 %) are agreed poor. This shows that quality of education provided in Madrasas are good and also, they are aware of quality of education provided in madrasa. Further 43 % students are agreed that awareness of Madrasa education be improved through educational programmer, 30 % through Community outreach, 25 % through Government initiatives and 2% increased media coverage. Twenty five percent students are aware through society and religious institutes, fifteen percent through media, society, internet, and religious institutions, forty seven percent from society thirteen percent school curriculum, society and religious institutions. This figure shows majority of the students are aware through society.

Mostly respondents are aware while thirteen percent are not aware and thirty percent are not sure. So total forty three percent students are not aware of government rules and regulations for establishing Madrasa. Only forty seven percent students are aware of Article 30 of the Indian constitution. (right to establish and administer educational institution for their choice) and a lot of students (total 53%) are unaware of Article 30 of the Indian constitution.

CONCLUSION

It is concluded that the level of awareness among the B.Ed. students of Jamia Millia Islamia related to the basic concept of madrasa as well as madrasa education is excellent. Further, they know that which kind of education and degree are being provided in madrasa and their values in modern time. The data also revealed that around eighty seven percent students of the B.Ed. of Jamia Millia Islamia are agreed that Madrasa plays a vital role in society but studying in Madrasa is a challenging task in 21st century in India regarding the adjustment of madrasa students in modern education. Therefore, there is need to enhance pedagogical skills of B.Ed. students for holistic development of madrasa students along with all students.

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